

MAJOR AREAS OF EXPERIENCES OF VISUAL ARTS STUDENTS IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN RIVERS STATE: ANALYSIS OF SOME SELECTED STUDENTS' ARTWORKS

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Abstract: *The students' application of skills, elements and principles of art to art practice testified that students have demonstrated that they have acquired some necessary skills for manipulating art tools and materials as a result of being exposed to industrial training. This shows that experiences on skill development of painting activities gained during industrial training has a high positive relationship with academic performance of visual arts students in tertiary institution in Rivers State. The aim of this paper was to explore the major areas of experiences of visual arts students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State and to analyze some selected students' artworks. The study adopted qualitative research method with the use of contextual analysis of data taken from extant literature within the scope of this study. The study therefore, revealed that students who were exposed to the process of industrial training gained practical skills extensively.*

Introduction

Industrial training has positive impact on students' visual art activities while on-the-job training. Performances of students are highly satisfactory, the students execute assignments given to them very well and quickly, once the environment for work is conducive. Besides, the students themselves also agreed that the program has equipped them with knowledge and skills which enabled them to improve in their academic performance or establish and run their

art studios effectively. This claim is validated by the high standard of the works which were reviewed in cause of this study. Pentious (2013) posits that, the study of the subject is sustained by the theories and practices in a wide range of visual arts forms. Students should progress along a continuum, from acquiring a range of different art experiences to work on a self-selected style, and from lecturer-directed learning to independent learning. Concurrent with increasing knowledge, skills and

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experiences in the visual arts. Students are encouraged to engage more broadly and deeply into their own personal pursuit of the visual arts and to consider career opportunities in the creative industry. According to Nwafor (2007), in the earlier stages of learning, students would be introduced to basic art concepts and the practice of art analysis and criticism. They would also have opportunities to develop increase independence and competence in the selection and application of a variety of media, and to acquire studio techniques. To prepare them for more independent learning in the later stages, students would explore ways of searching and researching, extending research into practical work. To broaden their views and strengthen their abilities for visual arts learning, students would also learn to relate art to its socio-cultural and historical context, as well as their own context. From the foundation of knowledge and skill acquired through teacher-directed learning, students should be encouraged to move into areas of individual exploration. Exploration work should be done in consultation with the teacher (Okoro, 2006; Ekpenyong, 2011 & Elijah, 2017) in various units of visual arts in relation to industrial training and enhancement of academic performance of student. Industrial training is an inevitable factor for the effective implementation of visual arts education. Bassey et al (2020), asserts that visual arts typically denotes such expressions as painting, sculpture, ceramics, textile and graphic designs. It deals

with aesthetics and the intellectual stimulation of the student. Based on the above backdrop, this study ex-rays the major areas of experiences of visual art students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State: analyzing some selected students' artworks.

Visual Arts Curriculum Objectives:

The objectives of visual arts curriculum are to:

1. Enrich student's aesthetics and arts experience.
2. Strengthen their abilities to appreciate and create various forms of visual art works aesthetically and critically.
3. Develop perceptual abilities, generic skills and meta-cognition through autonomous and open-ended processes of inquiry in visual art learning.
4. Enhance multiple perspectives, cultural and cross cultural understanding through exploration of the visual arts of diverse cultures.
5. Cultivate personal refinement, values and attitudes, self-identity and a sense of commitment towards the community, the nation and the world.
6. Acquire a foundation for pursuing educational and career opportunities in the visual arts and creative industry's lessons and art in general.

Importance of Visual Arts in Education

Visual arts can be a powerful discipline to support success through-out a student's education, both within and outside school settings (Denver, 2019). Students experience visual arts each day, whether through their own creativity or everyday objects, such as design a

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cereal box or logo of a favourite sports team. For students, engaging with visual arts might take place during an art class. As students learn to create, respond, connect to their surrounding and experiences, visual arts help them to gain skills that positively impact their experiences under the following headings.

1. Cultivate interest for learning.
2. Boost student's academic achievements.
3. Enhance the educational experience.

Visual Arts Education helps Students Develop Critical Thinking Skills

When students engage in critical thinking it will in turn lead to a deeper understanding of educational content – both within the arts and in other subject areas, thus;

- a. Visual arts education fosters creativity in students and increases student's encouragement.
- b. Strengthen critical thinking: Research indicates that when student engage with visual arts, in the classroom or out-side the classroom, they make positive gains in critical thinking skills.
- c. Encourages student's engagement: Teachers observed that students who participated in visual arts programs out-side the classroom or in the classroom tended to have more interest in the art and engagement in schools.
- d. Foster creativity: Researchers found out that students who study art tend to score higher on creativity measures.

Visual Arts Education Boosts Academic Achievement

When students engage in visual arts education, they can experience achievement in other facets of their education that they may not have otherwise experience. Research indicates that visual arts education can impact other areas of achievement in the following ways:

- a. Enhances writing quality and reading skills.
- b. Contribute to academic success in other areas of their studies.

Arts students are more likely than their non-arts peers have improved tests scores, researchers found that students participating in arts-rich curriculum performed better on proficiency tests in mathematics, science and social studies than students with less access to arts.

Visual Arts Education Enhances the Educational Experience of Students:

- a. Help students acquire communication skills, learners who engage in arts programs in their schools increase their listening, writing and speaking skills. This process occurs through discussing their personal arts work aloud and writing about arts.
- b. Impact students positively outside of academics. When students participate in the arts, their civic encouragement increases. Students with the high level of arts engagement are also more likely to participate in extra curriculum activities.

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Various Units of Visual Arts in Relation to Industrial Training and Enhancement of Academic Performance of Students

As earlier stated, Students Industrial Work Experience Scheme (SIWES) is an inevitable factor for the effective implementation of visual arts education. Visual Arts typically denotes such expressions as Painting, Sculpture, Ceramics, Textiles Design and Graphics Design (Bassey et

al, 2020). It deals with aesthetics and the intellectual stimulation of the students.

Analysis on the Mixed Media Painting by David Kembukem

The mixed media painting by David Kembukem portrays a young maiden who covered her face but reveals only her eyes, to showcase cultural mode of dressing of a Hausa/Fulani maiden in the Northern part of Nigeria

Plate 1

Title: I hide from what my eye see

Artist: David Kembukem

Medium: Net, oil and acrylic on canvas

Size: 121.92 by 121.92

Year: 2020

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In this work, 'I hide from what my eye sees' Kembukem used assorted media/materials to express himself. The artist adopted a realistic approach to the painting, representing every aspect of the face with the natural colour in mixed media. The message of the artist to the viewers is visually expressed on the face of the work. However, the interesting thing with the painting is that, if you wink your eyes in the right way, you begin to see hidden images and shapes around (Bandura, 1995; ITF, 2004 Awodun, 2005; Kolb, et al., 2005 and Barkley, 2006). Kembukem rendered work with energy using oil on canvas as a medium. A closer look at the painting reveals that the face was rendered with oil on canvas, while the background of the figure conveyed different colours of acrylic, making it mixed media painting. Its uniqueness lies in the skillful arrangements of fishing net to the canvas, with shades of colours on the face. As such, it portrays good application of blended colour by the artist. A display of light and shade was also seen in the painting. In trying to achieve the light and shade in this work, the interplay of oil paint and fishing net on the face, made the work reflect mixed media rendition with enamel paints and other synthetic materials.

Victory Orowoghene Idudu

Idudu, Victory Orowoghene's dexterity in painting is evident in "Green River" (a land of peace and growth) which has watershed of the river known as the Green River Basin. The theme which many visual artist sees from different

backgrounds, have explored and exploited using assorted media. The vividness of the entire seascape reveals the student's experiences in the painting in cause of his training in industrial training. The Green River is a beautiful seascape that revealed a beautiful serene environment, the foreground reveals boats fastened to a stuck on the shores of a supposed river and some are cut off from the scene of the artist's work. In the object region, one could notice local houses depicted colourfully with dominant yellow on the roof. The work reveals sunset of the evening, the sky was marked with brilliant blue and their casts could be seen on the ground suggesting a calm weather in a cool evening supposedly. While the background exposes a vegetation of uncultivated land with a big tree behind the houses and the sky was composed of green and yellow. The scene depicted by the artist indicates the two occupations of the riverine people; that is, farming and fishing. At the extreme right of the house is an extension or attachment of a smaller hot supposedly for relaxation or smoking of fish. The most significant aspect of the work is that the student's technique in colouration of the objects and the subjects in the picture plane and the balance so achieved. The vividness of the entire seascape reveals the maturity of the artist in painting.

The title of this painting is "Green River". The structure and composition of the painting largely deals on the physical appearance of the seascape. The structure of the painting has to do with the

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yellow and purple that dominates the sky; the green in the painting was used to detail the grass that surrounds the environment, while the brown dominated the foreground and the linear arrangement of the buildings in the painting. The artist achieved the painting by using brushes and acrylic colours on canvas and also considering the structure and composition of the painting, the elements and principles of art were largely put into consideration. In the composition and structural built of the painting, the use of yellow, green and purple shades of colour contributed in the arrangement of depth

and contrast. The use of colours to detail the figure in the painting was aimed at enhancing the aesthetics of the work and also binded by the principles of art in the work which are dominance, contrast, harmony and unity. The dexterous and skillful arrangement of the tree in the painting is interesting and commendable. While dark neutral colours like black was used to highlight the dark tones, especially in the trees and grasses. The idea is to make the painting outstanding and for easy identification. Colours contributed in the arrangement of depth and contrast.

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Plate 2.

Title: The Green River (A land of peace and growth)

Artist: Idudu Victory Orowoghene

Medium: paper mache and acrylic on board

Size: 30 by 30 inches

Year: 2019

Conclusively, in the painting works by David Kembukem and Idudu Victory Orowoghene (plates 4 and 5) depicted effective distribution and application of colours immensely and enhanced the aesthetic values as well as creating subtleness in the painting. For a painting to reflect the illusion of depth, it must harness the effective application of light and shade which is

evident in this works and it is largely expressed on these paintings.

Okwe Obinna; A Woman's Pride

However, skill development on sculpture activities has a high positive relationship with academic performance of sculpture students on industrial training. Thus, SWIES objectives in trainees of art programmes showed that the

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students are well equipped with: Entrepreneurial skills to become self-reliant in art practice, required knowledge and skills for problem-solving in matters related to art and design, Knowledge and manipulative skills for handling basic tools and equipment, ability to render technical support, especially in visual forms to industries or institutions that require art and design services. This can be seen in the art works of Okwe Obinna. In the work, a woman's pride Okwe captured a pregnant woman, the message Okwe intends to pass across to the viewers is visually expressed in a woman that is pregnant, revealing the pride of every woman. Women are the strongest, most resilient human being. Right from bearing a child, to dealing with the problems that arise monthly and yearly in raising the child bearing is awe worthy.

The strength to face the world, the strength to stand up for oneself, for her family and for her kids is in every woman's DNA. Women, of all sizes, ages and races are strong in their own right, This Okwe wants to pass across to his viewers "a woman's pride". The woman was presented in an appropriate position, though the woman is not fully captured. The structure and position of the sculptural piece were carefully composed to showcase the strength of a woman. The work is slightly smaller than life size status, and it was produced in fibre glass and metal. It bears a bronze colour which the student achieved with enamel paints. Formally, he controlled the drapery and anatomy fairly well. The student has used the artistic skills he acquired in the course of his training to present his work sculpturally

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Plate 3.

Artist: Okwe Obinna

Title: A woman's pride

Medium: Fibre glass and metal

Size: 16 inches

Year: 2020

The sculpture piece by Okwe "The praying hand" is the visual expression of praying hands which symbolise obedience, submission, sincerity, repentance, veneration and respect in regards to one's higher power. While the familiar praying hands posture of hands held pressed together in front of one's heart is often associated with christianity, it is also used by Jews, Hindu's and Buddhists. The sculptural piece reflects the student's experiences recreated in relief with fibre glass, The students express himself by exhibitng a good understanding of proportion and anatomy in the

modelling of the hand; this he did, by modelling palms to palm and bringng the palm together, which the viewers see as the praying hands. The descterity with which he handled the sculptural piece suggests that he is able to analyse and solve simple problems related to sculpture, and that he is equipped with skills that can enable him assist effectively in running a sculpture studio. The two works were done with fibre glass and metal respectively. While the woman's pride is in the round, the praying hand is in relief. Okwe was able to managed his media well to the extent that reveals that he is in control of his

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material. The relief sculpture is a portable framed work, measuring about 16 inches x 12 inches designed to hang on a wall like a painting work. On the other hand, the woman's pride is also a sculptural piece standing on a wooden base. Its composition is about 16 inches high and can be viewed in the round. It was observed that the student artists were able to generate concepts and used them based on a wide range of experiences they have had within and outside the school environments. The works have also proved that Okwe have the ability to initiate ideas

and actualise it in art as well as appropriately select and manipulate tools and equipment used in art practice. Plates 6 and 7, for example, are student's projects which showed how well the students can use both tools and materials to articulate their ideas in sculpture. This shows experiences on skill development in sculpture activities gained during industrial training has a moderate positive relationship with academic performance of visual arts students in tertiary institution in Rivers State.

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Okwe Obinna's Praying Hand

Plate 4.

Artist: Okwe Obinna

Title: Praying hand

Medium: Fibre glass

Size: 16 inches x 12 inches

Year: 2020

Furthermore, responses by students of visual arts in ceramics unit showed that there is overwhelming agreement among the students that industrial training has impacted positively in their artistic experiences due to their exposure to different methods of training by their industrial training site supervisor, such methods are demonstrations, projects, assignments by the site supervisors, also,

excursions to areas of interest and critique sessions are the practical training methods that are seen as effective methods of training visual arts students. This indicates that, the visual arts students have acquired some level of proficiency which enabled them to manipulate ceramics equipment such as potter's wheel and other tools and materials.

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Ikpo Godspower's Ceramic Works and Beautiful Azozo Princess

The works by Ikpo Godspower also reveal the extent the students have been able to integrate aesthetics into functional products. Plate 5 and 6 are ceramic works produced by Ikpo Godspower for the promotion of wisdom draw from the wealth of knowledge gained in the university environment, which are embedded in the curriculum. The student exhibited some proficiency in handling clay and other ceramic materials. While Godspower in (plate 6) portrayed the beautiful Azozo princess, showcasing her royalty, the princess was dressed in an appropriate traditional costume with a tunic of woven red coral beads round her head and neck. The production of the work did not only entail modeling, it also involved the use of artistic skills he acquired in the course of his training. Actually, the level of artistic skills the student has demonstrated in his ceramic works cannot be over emphasized. The ceramic works in plates 5-6 shows the students' abilities in exploring clay for the production of utilitarian

wares that exhibit formal aesthetic qualities. the works indicate that the student have acquired some level of proficiency which enabled him to manipulate ceramics equipments such as the potter's wheel to throw clay and kiln. The figures are glazed, hand-built decorative vessels while plate 6 is an ornamental polished plaque. The producer have displayed some proficiency in modeling them. In fact, in ceramics production generally, the student have not only explored clay and glazing method, they have also produced works which manifest some convincing evidence that they were exposed to different ceramic techniques and processes. Conclusively, the works revealed the extent to which the students have been able to integrate the experiences in the school and that they received during their industrial training. This shows that the skills developed from ceramics activities through industrial training has a high positive relationship with academic performance of visual arts students in tertiary institution in Rivers Stat

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Plate 5.

Artist: Ikpo Godspower

Title: Wisdom Pot

Medium: Clay (Polished Pot)

Year: 2020

Anthonette Dagogo's Corona Virus and Charity Iwedi's Different Heart

Textile students who were interviewed, indicated that there is moderate relationship between experiences gained and skills acquired from textile activities during industrial training which the student trainee could apply on his own initiative and ability to become self-reliant. Thus, the textile works by Anthonette, Charity

Plate 6.

Artist: Ikpo Godspower

Title: Azozo Princess

Medium: Clay ware

Year: 2020

and Gold, due to their exposure to it was able to reveal some evidence of proficiency in translating the students ideas into concrete imageries through textile design. Plates 7 - 8 are tie and dye, batik, prints and tapestry are produced by the students. They are variegated textile designs which took the students through experimentation not only in the techniques of tying and dyeing fabrics, but also through the

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process of selection of good colour schemes. In weaving, the students also exploited different weaving materials and apparatus which yielded textiles and crafts of good quality and which also afforded them the opportunities of gaining the fundamental skills in weaving technology. In all, the textiles are testimonies to the artistic skills which the students have imbibed and which the textile industries can harness. They are also evidence that the students have acquired some requisite skills that will enable them become self-reliant upon graduation.

Plate 7.

Artist: Anthonette Dagogo

Title: Corona Virus

Medium: Dye on Fabric

Size: 5 yards

Year: 2020

The students have also explored some methods and materials of textile design and production. They were exposed to tie and dye technique, batik making, weaving process and printing on fabrics. This shows that experience on skill development in textile design activities gained during industrial training has a moderate positive relationship with academic performance of visual arts students in tertiary institution in Rivers State

Plate 8.

Artist: Charity Iwedi

Title: Different heart

Medium: Dye on Fabric

Size: 5 yards

Year: 2020

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Gold Nwogu's: Landscape

Plate 9

Artist: Gold Nwogu

Title: Landscape

Medium: Wool on loom

Size: 24 by 36 inches

Year: 2020

Owhondah F. F. Wisdom's: Academic Saga

Industrial training programme of the Graphic students inculcate in the trainees the requisite skills and knowledge that equip the students in graphics unit with initiative and ability to become self-reliant. The graphic works in plates 8 - 9 demonstrate some evidence of fair craftsmanship. Here, Owhondah visually expresses himself to his viewers. The student

Plate 10.

Artist: Owhondah F. F. Wisdom

Title: Aroma of Dance

Medium: Litho ink print on paper

Size: 35x30cm

Year: 2020

also explored techniques in poster design and production. To a novice, the word Saga may seem confusing as it is normally associated with some horrible and distasteful events or happening. Academic Saga is often associated with something negative or scandalous. No, academic saga is not used in these senses, the positive meaning of the word academic saga as the student trainee used it here is never thought in negative as in most cases, Saga is something

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good; it is a narrative that is believed on strict adherence to in pursuit of excellence, academic excellence in this case. On the background of the poster is a faded image of a University, Federal Government and ASUU negotiation, while the students probably looked and hoped for a better future. The poster which was created with poster colour on cardboard paper had the idea to inform the viewers that Federal Government and ASUU can resolve their differences through negotiation and not through strike. Besides, the student's work in print making reveal some evidence of proficiency in translating their ideas into concrete imageries via creative printing media. Plates 10 is monochromatic linocuts which the students produced using linoleum materials. Although the prints appeared quite

rigid, they readily convey to the viewer the concreteness of the figures and objects therein depicted in a manner that is the characteristics of many successful prints.

The works indicated the extent to which industrial training student have been able to integrate aesthetics into functional products. Actually, the level of artistic skill that students have demonstrated in their graphic works shows the extent to which SIWES has contribution in bridging the gap between the theories and the practices. This shows that experience on skill development of graphics design activities gained during industrial training has a high positive relationship with academic performance of visual arts students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

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Owhondah F.F. Wisdom's: Academic Saga

Plate 11

Artist: Owhondah F. F. Wisdom

Title: Academic Saga

Medium: Poster colour on paper

Size: 24x18cm

Year: 2020

Conclusion

The works selected and discussed here covered the major areas of experiences of visual arts students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. The students who were exposed to the process of industrial training gained practical skills extensively. The areas the students were exposed to include sculpture, painting, ceramics, textiles design and graphic design

works. Works in this collection were chosen from the students' given assignments and final year studio projects. They were ideas the student's developed from their socio-cultural experiences, and produced in various media. Selection of the works were based on variety of considerations which include theme, media, style and content. The works are to help in giving some insight into the extent to which the aim

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and objectives of the industrial training programme are achieved. At the end of their training, the students would be able to: effectively run their own art studios, analyze and solve simple artistic problems related to art; maintain, select and manipulate tools and equipment used in art profession.

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